

*Forage Crops-based Feeds on the Growth and Reproductive Performance of Rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*)*

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine the growth and reproductive performance of rabbit fed with forage crops-based feeds in terms of the bodyweight gain, amount of concentrates and forage intake, feed conversion ratio, onset of puberty, conception rate, number of bunnies per doe, survival rate and liveweight of bunnies 30 days after birth. The study was laid-out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four treatments replicated four times. The data gathered were analysed using the Analysis of Variance and those with significant results were subjected to Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Results revealed that forage crops-based feeds using sweet potato significantly influenced the gain in weight, concentrate and forage intake, and feed conversion ratio of rabbits. Significant results also noted on the reproductive performance in terms of the survival rate 30 days after birth; but insignificant results noted for the onset of puberty, conception rate, and the number of bunnies per doe. Rabbit fed with sweet potato (*Ipomea batatas*) leaves based feeds plus concentrates significantly gained weight after three, four, six and seven weeks from those with napier (*Pennisetum purpureum*) and guinea grass (*Panicum maximum*) but after eight weeks it was obtained by rabbit fed with guinea grass. Highest concentrate and forage intake from those fed with sweet potato plus concentrates, significantly higher from other treatments and significantly efficient converter after three and four weeks of experimentation. Sweet potato based feeds resulted to shortest onset of puberty, highest conception rate, produced most number of bunnies per doe, high survival rate 30 days after birth, and produced the heavy bunnies.

Keywords: *Rabbit, forage crops, growth, reproductive, performance*

INTRODUCTION

Rabbit production is popular not only in the Philippines but in all developing countries. It contributes to improve nutrition and the economy of small holders both as a source of animal protein as well as source of extra income Luyen, et al (2012).

The Department of Agriculture (DA) also sees rabbit meat as a potential replacement for pork as they are also a good source of protein, Medenilla (2021). Today, one of the major factors that influence production is the cost of feeds. That is why, researchers aim to lessen the cost of production by utilizing the available resources that can lessen or reduce the cost of feeds and increase the profit. The best example of feeds that can reduce cost yet can satisfy the nutritional requirements of rabbit are the different species of forage crops such as sweet potato leaves, guinea grass and napier which are available in the locality and can be produced in large quantity throughout the year.

According to Veneracion (2017) rabbit production is really profitable when managed properly because of its potential as healthy meat source and a source of income. It requires little space and can be raised in small area for backyard raising. These animals are gentle and quiet and can easily manage by the caretaker. Rabbit has simple management system, simple and affordable to start a business and considered with high production capacity; medium-sized breeds that are ideal for meat production and can be bred at 6 months old with a gestation period of 28-32 days. The estimated world production of rabbit meat is 1,200,000 metric tonnes, Lebas, et al (1997).

In rabbit production, selection of breed is very important for market and meat production. There are several breeds of rabbit in the world, but the most popular breed that holds the title of being the top breeder for meat purpose due to overall productivity for both the processor and the growers is the New Zealand White Rabbit. This is commonly accepted as the outstanding rabbit by meat producers because it grows rapidly, converts feed economically, and is very prolific (A Pet Love Guide to Rabbits & Guinea Pig 2000).

Hence, the researcher found it challenging to conduct a research study on the growth and reproductive performance of rabbit fed with forage crop-based feeds.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The study was laid-out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four treatments, replicated four times. The study used sixteen female rabbits (does) as experimental animals fed with forage crops-based feeds using 15% of the bodyweight and 3% of the bodyweight for the amount of concentrates. The treatments were: Treatment A-15% sweet potato + 3% concentrates; B-15% napier + 3% concentrates; C-15% guinea grass + 3% concentrates; and D-15% combination of the three forages + 3% concentrates laid-out in a RCBD raised in an elevated experimental cages with four heads per treatment. To prevent biases, the experimental animals were produced from tested does or female rabbit produced in one kindling. Two months old rabbit were used as experimental animals and they were fed with forage crop based-feeds. Feeding was done two times a day both forage crops and concentrates. All data gathered such as body weight gain, amount of concentrates and forage intake, feed conversion ratio, onset of puberty, rate of conception, number of bunnies per do, bunnies survival rate after 30 days after birth, and liveweight of bunnies after 30 days of age.

Data Collection Procedure. Data gathered were analysed using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and significant results were subjected to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). There were sixteen experimental cages used where experimental does or female rabbits were placed and four separated cages were also used four bucks or male rabbits used during breeding period. Feeding was done based on the body weight while watering was done Ad libitum. Cleaning of feeding and watering troughs was done regularly to prevent the occurrence of diseases and the feces or rabbit wastes was placed in the sack to prevent the proliferation of flies and other insects. The study was conducted for fifteen (15) weeks in which experimental animals were fed with forage crops based feeds using sweet potato leaves, napier grass and guinea grass following the treatment descriptions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result revealed that in terms of liveweight gain, rabbit fed with sweet potato-based feeds plus concentrates obtained the highest gain in weight heavier from those in other treatments. It was also recorded that rabbit fed with sweet potato based-feeds significantly gained weight after three weeks which was heavy from those rabbits in other treatments except from rabbit fed with combination of three forages. The same result after four weeks of the study but the weight of rabbit was significantly heavier from other treatments. Significant result was also noted after six, and seven weeks of experimentation that feeding of sweet potato to rabbit resulted to significant gain in weight over from those fed with guinea and napier grass including those fed with a combination of three forages. After eight weeks rabbit fed with guinea grass obtained the highest gain in weight significant from those with sweet potato, napier grass and with those fed with a combination of three forages. The result confirmed to the result of Abonyi, et al 2012 that the use of 50% sweet potato leaves and 50% concentrates resulted to optimum growth and reduced overall cost of production based on their trial on effects of feeding sweet potato (*Ipomea batatas*) leaves on growth performance and nutrient digestibility of rabbits. The result justified to the claimed of Duke and Reed that *Ipomea batatas* is best for farm animals in which dried vine of sweet potato contains 12.6 g protein higher from the protein content of napier and guinea grass of 8.2 and 5.9, respectively. It also supports to the statement of Duke 1993 that sweet potato is considered as feed for animals in which 3 kilograms of sweet potato leaves is equivalent to 1 kilogram of corn with a food value rated to 95-100% that of corn and also the dry vines of this plant have a feed value comparable from that of alfalfa when use as forage to animals. It was added that sweet potato vines and foliage can be fed to cattle, sheep, goats, pigs and rabbits and can be supplied to cattle during the periods of water stress (drought season) according to Scott cited by the same author. It was further explained that sweet potato can be fed fresh, dried or ensiled and makes a very palatable silage with a pleasant fruity smell according to Lebot cited by the same author and this also in support to the findings of Defang, et al 2013 that feed intake and liveweight during lactation was significantly higher from diet containing sweet potato concentrate meal and *Echinocloa pyramidalis* compared from other treatments; while stillbirth and gestation length were comparable in all treatments based on their study on the reproductive performance of local rabbit does on sweet potato concentrate meal to forage combination under tropical condition.

Table 1. Weekly liveweight gain of rabbit fed with forage-crop based feeds (kg)

No. of Weeks	Treatment				Level of Significance
	A	B	C	D	
1	0.11	0.08	0.05	0.14	ns
2	0.22	0.16	0.17	0.12	ns
3	0.19 ^a	0.09 ^b	0.13 ^b	0.15 ^a	*
4	0.38 ^a	0.18 ^b	0.10 ^c	0.20 ^b	**
5	0.13	0.11	0.12	0.18	ns
6	0.24 ^a	0.09 ^b	0.13 ^b	0.3 ^b	*
7	0.15 ^a	0.11 ^b	0.08 ^b	0.11 ^b	*
8	0.09 ^b	0.09 ^b	0.16 ^a	0.09 ^b	*
9	0.03 ^b	0.04 ^b	0.15 ^a	0.06 ^b	ns
10	-0.03	0.06	0.11	0.02	ns
11	-0.35 ^b	-0.05 ^a	-0.20 ^{ab}	-0.20 ^a	ns
12	0.04	-0.09	-0.05	0.04	ns
13	.00	-0.02	-0.05	0.05	ns
14	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	ns
15	-1.76	0.01	-0.46	0.00	ns

In terms of the concentrate intake, the result revealed that the highest concentrate consumption was noted from those rabbit fed with sweet potato based-feeds followed with those fed with a combinations of the three forage crops such as sweet potato, napier and guinea grass and the least was recorded from those fed with napier grass. Significant result was noted after eight, nine and ten weeks of the study in which rabbit fed with sweet potato-based feeds plus concentrates consumed more concentrates which was significantly more than those rabbit fed with napier, guinea grass and with those with combination of three forage. It was also further observed that after eleven to fifteen weeks of experiment, the highest concentrate consumption noted from those rabbit fed with a combination of the three forages but the amount was almost the same due to insignificant result. The result conformed to the findings Anonyo, et al (2012) that the highest final liveweight of rabbit fed with sweet potato shows that the highest was obtained from those fed with 50% sweet potato leaves same with those in the control group or feed with concentrates in which researcher recommended 50% to obtain optimum growth and to reduce cost of production in rabbit production.

Table 2. Weekly concentrate intake of rabbit fed with forage-crop based feeds (kg)

No. of Weeks	Treatment				Level of Significance
	A	B	C	D	
1	0.26	0.24	0.23	0.25	ns
2	0.31	0.28	0.27	0.28	ns
3	0.35	0.29	0.29	0.31	ns
4	0.40	0.33	0.31	0.35	ns
5	0.43	0.35	0.34	0.39	ns
6	0.48	0.37	0.36	0.41	ns
7	0.51	0.40	0.38	0.44	ns
8	0.53 ^a	0.42 ^b	0.41 ^b	0.46 ^b	*
9	0.54 ^a	0.42 ^b	0.43 ^b	0.46 ^b	*
10	0.54 ^a	0.44 ^b	0.45 ^b	0.47 ^b	*
11	0.46	0.45	0.41	0.46	ns
12	0.47	0.43	0.40	0.48	ns
13	0.47	0.43	0.39	0.48	ns
14	0.48	0.43	0.40	0.49	ns
15	0.43	0.44	0.40	0.49	ns

For forage consumption of rabbit fed with forage crop-based feeds revealed that the highest consumption was obtained by rabbit fed with sweet potato-based feeds from the start up to fourteen weeks of the study. It was noted that significant results was obtained after three weeks of the study in which the consumption of those rabbit with sweet potato significantly higher from those rabbit in other treatments. It was also found that that significant result in the forage consumption was noted after five

to eleven weeks of experimentation that consumption of sweet potato was higher in which rabbit consumed significantly higher from those rabbit fed with napier, guinea grass including those rabbit fed with a combination of the three forages. The highest total forage consumption was recorded from those with sweet potato and the least was consumed by those rabbit fed with guinea grass. The result of the study consistent to the findings of Mohammad, et al (2020) that feeding napier with concentrates showed significantly lower feeds from those rabbit in the control group. It was added that Napier is considered as suitable forage for ruminants due to its high yielding and nutritive value.

Table 3. Weekly forage intake of rabbit fed with forage-crop based feeds (kg)

No. of Weeks	Treatment				Level of Significance
	A	B	C	D	
1	1.01	0.94	0.83	0.90	ns
2	1.14	1.08	0.84	0.99	ns
3	1.37	1.26	1.02	1.14	*
4	1.61	.14	1.10	1.28	ns
5	1.88 ^a	1.51 ^b	1.20 ^c	1.43 ^{bc}	**
6	2.03 ^a	1.64 ^b	1.37 ^b	1.67 ^b	*
7	2.29 ^a	1.41 ^b	1.58 ^b	.86 ^b	*
8	2.44 ^a	1.57 ^b	1.62 ^b	1.98 ^b	*
9	2.54 ^a	1.64 ^b	1.79 ^b	2.06 ^b	**
10	2.60 ^a	1.69 ^b	1.86 ^b	2.12 ^b	**
11	2.54 ^a	1.90 ^b	1.88 ^b	2.11 ^b	**
12	2.17	1.79	1.79	2.10	ns
13	2.17	1.64	1.72	2.14	ns
14	2.19	1.99	1.52	2.15	ns
15	0.30	1.81	1.55	1.70	ns

For the feed conversion ratio, the result revealed that efficient feed converter was noted from those rabbit fed with sweet potato plus concentrates after 2,3,4,6, and 9 weeks of the study. It was recorded that combination of the three forages was efficient after one and seven weeks of the study. Significant result was also noted after three weeks in which feeding with sweet potato plus concentrates was significantly efficient from those in other treatments, but after four weeks the efficient converter was also with sweet potato but it was found out that the result was comparable from those rabbit fed with napier and those with combination of three forage crops; but significantly efficient from those rabbit fed with guinea grass. The feed conversion ratio was computed based on the dry matter content of the concentrates and based on the 14% moisture content of the forages. The result justified the composition of sweet potato according to the report of Hug et al 1993 that it contains 90.7 dry matter; 12.6 protein; 3.3 fat; 19.1 fiber; 45.5 NFE; 10.2 mineral matter; 8.9 digestible protein and 51.7% total digestible nutrients. In support to the statement of Panhwar that rabbits are herbivorous and eat most green food, grains, and roots that help rabbits become more vigorous and healthier. The result also did not conform to the report of the CSIR that guinea grass is valuable for pasture, green soilage, hay and silage which is best palatable in younger stages tending to become coarser and less readily eaten by cattle at it matures. It was also explained that guinea grass juice stimulate the movements in isolated intestines of goats and other ruminant animals and it can counteracts the inhibitory effects on the intestine and may therefore prove useful in preventing tympanities in cattle.

Table 4. Feed conversion ratio of rabbit fed with forage-crop based feeds (kg)

No. of Weeks	Treatment				Level of Significance
	A	B	C	D	
1	4.75	6.32	10.61	3.91	ns
2	2.51	3.40	2.93	8.60	ns
3	3.26 ^b	8.45 ^a	3.71 ^a	3.51 ^a	*
4	2.80 ^b	3.22 ^{ab}	6.50 ^a	3.00 ^{ab}	*
5	6.47	8.32	4.61	3.79	ns
6	3.75	9.05	5.69	5.47	ns
7	8.81	10.16	9.42	7.31	ns
8	16.33	9.71	5.56	14.14	ns
9	4.87	5.58	5.05	16.70	ns

For the onset of puberty, the result revealed that feeding of forage crops based feeds did not significantly influenced the onset of puberty of the rabbit but the result shows that the early to reach puberty was those fed with sweet potato based feeds, the same from those animals fed with a combination of the three forages. It was also found out that the longest or delayed to demonstrate was noted from those with napier grass based feeds.

For the rate of conception, the result revealed that rabbit fed with sweet potato and guinea grass feed-based feeds obtained 100% conception rate and the least was those with napier plus concentrates. Based on the statistical analysis, the result revealed there were no significant noted among treatment means.

For the number of bunnies, the result revealed that the most number of bunnies was recorded from those rabbit fed with sweet potato based feeds plus concentrates and the least were noted from those with guinea grass. The statistical analysis revealed that there were no significant differences noted from those with forage crops based feeds and those with combination of the three forage crops plus concentrates.

For the survival rate, the highest survival after 30 days after birth shows that rabbit with sweet potato plus concentrates was still the highest, but the statistical analysis shows that the result was comparable from those animals fed with other forage crops including those with a combination of the three forage crops plus concentrates. This findings justified to the claims of Antia, et al 2012 that sweet potato leaves contains crude protein, crude fat, crude fibre, ash, carbohydrate, moisture contents and calorific values with 24.85%, 4.90%, 7.20%, 11.10%, 51.95%, 82.21% and 351.30 kcal respectively. They added that the vitamin composition. The result supports to the findings of Defang, et al that does fed with sweet potato and *Imperata cylindrica* combination had better intake, kindling rate and litter weight at weaning.

For the number of bunnies, the most bunnies was produced by does or female rabbit fed with sweet potato, followed with those fed with combination and the least was noted from those fed with napier grass. No significant result was noted on the number of bunnies of those fed with forage crops and those with combination of the three forage crops.

Table 5. Reproductive performance of rabbit fed with forage crops-based feeds

Treatment	Onset of puberty (day)	Conception rate (%)	No. of bunnies per doe (head)	Bunnies survival rate (%)	Weight of bunnies (kg)
A	96.00	100.00	6.00	95.75 ^a	0.41
B	107.00	68.75	5.25	86.50 ^b	0.27
C	102.25	100.00	4.50	83.75 ^b	0.33
D	102.75	87.50	5.00	77.50 ^c	0.40

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the study, the researcher concluded that forage crops-based feeds using sweet potato is influential on the growth and reproductive performance of rabbit. The nutrient content of sweet potato influenced the nutrient requirements of rabbit resulted to an efficient feed converter, produced more number of bunnies, high survival rate and heavy weight of bunnies. Hence; sweet potato can be used as feeds to rabbit to attain maximum growth and produced more and healthy bunnies. Similar studies should be conducted using same forages with different methods of feeding.

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